

A Study on The Prevalence of Cyberbullying Among youth in North 24 Parganas District

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Abstract: *The purpose of this present study is to examine the prevalence of cyberbullying among youth in North 24 Parganas District. The study also investigates the common forms and platforms of cyberbullying and its impact on mental and emotional wellbeing among youth. It also compares the experience between gender. A quantitative descriptive survey was adopted for this study. The study uses a stratified convenience sampling method to select participants. Data were collected from 200 students age between (15-18) in two schools. A researcher made structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale was used, covering prevalence, forms and platforms, impact and gender difference of cyberbullying experience. Percentage, standard deviation, Mean & t-test were used for data analysis. The findings revealed that majority of youth in North 24 Parganas District are affected by cyberbullying, showing a high level of prevalence and it occurs various forms and platforms such as social media and other messaging platforms. It also indicates that cyberbullying has a moderate to high negative impact on mental and emotional wellbeing of youth. The study also revealed that there was a significant difference in cyberbullying experience between male and female youth in North 24 Parganas District. The study concludes that cyberbullying is a very severe issue among youth, this shows the need to create awareness, take preventive measures and guide youth how to use digital platforms safely in their daily life.*

Keyword: *Cyberbullying, Prevalence & Youth*

Introduction:

With the rapid expansion of digital technology in 21st century the use of internet, smart phones, and social media has progressed significantly among youth. In India youth are highly active on platform such as social networking, messaging applications, and online games. While these platforms present opportunities for communication, learning, and entertainment, they have also given rise to new forms of harmful behaviour.

The way of people communication has changed greatly in the last few decades because of advancement in technology. Teenagers and adolescents are particularly vulnerable to the pitfalls of technology, as they have many opportunities to get into the virtual world. Their thirst for knowledge and lack of security expertise exposes them to cyber-technologies because of their time constraints and poor judgment of what is right and wrong. This can lead to them becoming victims of cyber-attacks (Mondal, et, al.)

Cyberbullying is an aggressive, intentional act, or behaviour that is carried out by a group or an individual, using electronic forms of contact such as SNS, instant messengers' digital images/messages repeatedly, and overtime against a victim who cannot easily defend him or herself (Mukherjee, et, al, 2019). Cyberbullying differs from traditional bullying primarily in terms of the medium and scope of harassment. Unlike traditional bullying, which typically occurs face-to-face or in physical environments such as school or neighbourhood settings, cyberbullying takes place online through digital platforms such as social media, messaging apps, email, or online forums. This digital aspect means that cyberbullying can happen at any time and reach a much wider audience than traditional bullying (Tripathi, et, al., 2024).

India has witnessed a sharp rise in cybercrimes recently, with over 33% of

children reported to experience Internet harassment, including cyberbullying. Cyberbullying is now recognized as a serious public health issue affecting adolescents' psychological development and potentially extending into adulthood (Parappil, et, al.,2026).

Prevalence means how common something is in a particular group at specific time. It refers to the percentage or number of youths who experience cyberbullying in North 24 Parganas district. The prevalence of cyber bullying and its impact on youth has hardly been studied even though it has been anecdotally happened on Internet particularly on online match making and dating websites, harassment in different forms and hidden and masked identities. (Parveen, et, al., 2019)

Youth" refers to the transitional period between childhood and adulthood, typically defined by the United Nations as persons aged 15–24 years. It represents a phase of life characterized by high energy, transition to independence, and rising autonomy. It is often a key demographic focus for development, employment, and policy-making. Childhood and adolescence are not only periods of growth, but also of emerging risk taking. Young people during these periods are particularly vulnerable and cannot fully understand the connection between behaviours and consequences (Zhu, et, al.,2021).

The corona virus pandemic is forcing people all over the world to practice social distancing and stay home and children are adjusting to e-learning. Some researchers have documented the effects of cyber victimization, which has been associated with academic and emotional problems, lowered self-esteem, lower psychological well-being, and lower perceptions of school safety (Oanh, et, al., 2021).

This study aims to explore the prevalence of cyberbullying among youth in North 24 Parganas District. In the Context of increasing internet and social media use, the study aims to identify the common problem of cyberbullying and understand its impact on mental and emotional well-being of young people. This study also intends to provide useful data to create awareness and support effective preventive measure.

Review Of Related Literature:

In the Indian and abroad context, numerous studies have investigated to explore the prevalence of cyberbullying among youth. Popovic', Djuric' & Cvetkovic (2011) examines that the prevalence of cyberbullying among adolescents: A case study of middle schools in Serbia, the study revealed that most of the students used the Internet on a daily basis and that almost all of them possess their own mobile telephones. On average, 10% of students aged 11- to 15-years-old reported that they have cyberbullied others online, whilst 20% of them were victims of cyberbullying. The most common types of victimization reported by students were denigration and harassment, and most of the cyberbullying took the form of harassment. There were significant gender differences in cyberbullying, with male students reporting higher levels of bullying others and being victimized by cyberbullies than females. Mukherjee, Sinha, De, Misra, Pal, & Mondal (2019) investigated that Cyberbullying among Late Adolescent: A Cross-sectional Study in Two Higher Secondary Schools of Kolkata, West Bengal, this study finds that results were analyzed using SPSS version 20. About 210 (82.7%) students were using any form of social networking site and out of which 22 (10.5%) students were cyberbullied. Among those who were cyberbullied, the majority (16 [72.7%]) had no opinion and more than half (15 [68.2%]) sought their friends' help. Cyberbullying

is emerging as a newer social problem in our country, where students' lack of awareness and understanding of it results in underreporting of cyberbullying incidents. Parveen, Shahzad & Altaf (2019) reviewed that Prevalence of Cyber Bullying and its Effect on Adolescents: A Literature Review, The present study has synthesised current literature on:

- i) prevalence of cyber bullying among adolescents
- ii) huge level of cyber bullying occurrences in educational institutions
- iii) people who are more prone to be the victims and perpetrators
- iv) effects of cyber bullying on adolescence
- v) preventive measures for the wellbeing of Pakistani adolescents.

In this article, the researcher reviews the literature related to cyber bullying conducted between the years from 2000 to 2019. Goswamee & Kakoti (2019) explored that, Prevalence of cyber bullying victimization among the school going adolescents in Kamrup district-a study, the findings of the study bring to light that cyber bullying is prevalent among the school going adolescents and girls were found to be mostly bullied. Though teachers mostly discussed about the issue of cyber bullying and cyber security but victims of cyber bullying discuss it with their friends Oanh, (2021), explores that The Prevalence of Cyberbullying among Adolescents: A Case Study of Middle Schools in Vietnam, the results show that most of the students used the Internet daily and that almost all of them possess mobile telephones. On average, 7% of students reported that they have cyberbullied others online, whilst 14% of them were victims of cyberbullying. There were not any significant gender differences in cyberbullying and being victimized by cyberbullies than females. Zhu, Huang, Evans and Zhang (2021), examined that, the prevalence rates of cyberbullying preparation ranged from 6.0 to 46.3%, while the rates of cyberbullying victimization ranged from 13.99 to 57.5%, based on 63 references. Verbal violence was the most common type of cyberbullying.

Fourteen risk factors and three protective factors were revealed in this study. Ceetakoru & Kalasapati, (2022) investigated Cyber Bullying – A Cross Sectional Study on The Prevalence and Ramifications of This Growing Enigma in Indian Adolescents, the analysis of this study revealed that 201 students that amounted to 64.4% of the respondents had experienced cyber bullying as victims in one way or another. These significant findings reflect a rise in the number of victims and bullies in the cyber world, proving that this fairly new phenomenon requires further research and needs to be looked into to explore ways to prevent, curb and overcome it in the future. Javed, Ahmed & Faisal examined that A comprehensive study on prevalence of cyberbullying and its impact on youths and adults, the survey has responses from all types of age groups Tweens, Teens, Youths, and Adults for identifying the prevalence of cyberbullying across the nation, but now there is an advent of a new add-on workplace cyberbullying. Dubey & Halder explored that the pattern of Cyberbullying among adolescents in India: An Exploratory study, findings suggested that 76 percent of female and 85 percent male adolescents have witnessed cyber bullying, 38 percent of adolescents have been victim of cyberbullying, at least once in their lifetime where 13 percent females and 3 percent males were bullied in such a manner that it has affected their ability to learn and feel safe in school. Further, it was found that 6 percent adolescent females and 14 percent adolescent males have cyberbullied others once in lifetime. 10 % of the Indian male adolescents participate in cyber bullying with preferred medium as massive multiplayer games (warcraft, guild of war). Mridha, Ashrafuzzaman &

Sara (2024), examined that Uncovering the Prevalence and Consequences of Cyberbullying Among Female Students as Virtual Violence in Bangladesh the findings reveal that 66.6% of respondents are from middle-income families, 24.4% from higher-income families, and 8% from lower-income families. Alarmingly, all respondents reported experiencing cyberbullying or harassment online, with 72% victimized weekly and 86% daily. Inappropriate comments were encountered by 83.3%, primarily on Facebook (87.77%), Messenger (76%) and others chat-based app and online website. The psychological impact is significant, with 7.8% of respondents experiencing high levels of depression and 48.8% suffering from sleep disturbances. Additionally, 43 respondents reported a reduction in their reputation due to online harassment. The study underscores the urgent need for enhanced digital literacy and awareness, recommending initiatives by the government and the ICT division of Bangladesh to mitigate the effects of cyberbullying. Marianathan, Ethiraj, Rajendran Kumar, Marudan, Lakshmanan & Rajamoorthy (2025), examined that Awareness and resilience among Indian adolescents on cyberbullying, the study results indicated significant improvements in the experimental group's awareness and coping scores after educational sessions. These findings demonstrate the effectiveness of such interventions, emphasizing the need for further research with larger samples. Parappil, Lalu2, Ravi, Thergaonkar, Malik, & Swain (2026), examined that, Prevalence and Correlates of Cyberbullying Among Adolescents in a Higher Secondary School in Kochi Military Station, the result of this study finds that the prevalence of cyberbullying victimization was 32.4%, whereas 7.2% reported perpetration of cyberbullying. About 51% had witnessed cyberbullying, and 3.4% stated that it affected their academic performance or sense of safety. Common forms included threatening messages or impersonation (18.3%), hurtful religious or ethnic remarks (6.6%), and sexually suggestive comments (1.7%). Abnormal SDQ scores indicating emotional or behavioural difficulties were present in 60% of participants. Multivariate analysis identified male gender, history of mental illness, poor childhood experiences, and abnormal SDQ scores as significant independent predictors of cyberbullying victimization.

Objective:

1. To measure the prevalence of cyberbullying among youth in North 24 Parganas District.
2. To identify the common forms and platforms of cyberbullying in North 24 Parganas District.
3. To examine the impact of cyberbullying on mental and emotional wellbeing of youth in North 24 Parganas District.
4. To compare cyberbullying experience based on gender. (male vs female).

Hypothesis:

- **Ho1** : Cyberbullying is not significantly prevalent among youth in North 24 parganas district.
- **Ho2** : There are no significant differences in the forms and platforms of cyberbullying among youth.
- **Ho3** : Cyberbullying has no significant impact on mental and emotional wellbeing of youth.
- **Ho4** : There is no significant difference in cyberbullying experience between male and female students.

Methodology:

This study employed a quantitative descriptive survey research design to ex-

amine the Prevalence of Cyberbullying among youth in North 24 Parganas District. The study uses a stratified convenience sampling method to select participants. Data were collected from 200 students age between (15-18) in two West Bengal board schools. A structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale was used, covering prevalence, forms and platforms, impact and gender difference of cyberbullying experience was prepared by the researcher. The collected data were analyzed using percentage, mean, standard deviation and t –test were used to compare the difference between male and female students. The result was presented in tables for easy understanding.

Result & Interpretation:

Ho1: Cyberbullying is not significantly prevalent among youth in North 24 parganas district.

TABLE 1 : PREVELENCE OF CYBERBULLYING AMONG YOUTH IN NORTH 24 PARGANAS DISTRICT.

Category	Number of Respondent	Percentage	Remarks
Total	200	100%	Total sample of the study
Experienced Cyberbullying Average Score >3	156	78%	High Prevalence
Not Experienced Cyberbullying Average Score <3	44	22%	Low prevalence

Table 1 shows the prevalence of cyberbullying among youth in North 24 parganas District. The findings of this study reveal that out of 200 respondents, 156 (78%) was experienced cyberbullying, while 44(22%) was not experienced cyberbullying, based on an average score greater than 3.

This finding indicates that majority of youth in North 24 parganas district are affected by cyberbullying, showing a high level of prevalence in the study area. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho1), which states that cyberbullying is not significantly prevalent among youth is rejected.

Ho2 : There are no significant differences in the forms and platforms of cyberbullying among youth.

TABLE 2: FORMS & PLATFORMS OF CYBERBULLYING AMONG YOUTH IN NORTH 24 PARGANAS

Serial	Forms & Platforms	>3 Responses Frequency	percentage	Remarks
1	Harassment	141	70.5%	High Prevalence
2	Rumors	165	82.5%	Very High prevalence
3	Impersonation	189	89.5%	Very High prevalence
4	Stalking	144	72%	High Prevalence
5	Offensive comments	128	64%	Moderate Prevalence
6	Social Media	175	87.5%	Very High Prevalence
7	WhatsApp	168	84%	Very High Prevalence
8	Gaming	101	50.5%	Low Prevalence
9	Multiple platform	159	79.5%	High Prevalence
10	Anonymous	142	71%	High Prevalence

Table 2 shows the different forms and platforms of cyberbullying among

youth in North 24 Parganas District. The result indicate that impersonate (89.5%), social media (87.5%) whatsapp (84%) and rumours (82.5%) have very high prevalence, which means these are the most common forms and platforms of cyberbullying. Forms like harassment (70.5%), stalking (72%), multiple platforms (79.5%) and anonymous platforms (71%) show high prevalence, indicating that cyberbullying is common in these areas.

Offensive comments (64%) show moderate prevalence, while gaming (50.5%) shows low prevalence, that means it is less common to other forms and platforms

Overall, the result indicate that cyberbullying is common and occurs mostly through social media and communication platforms.

TABLE 3 : Simple Rule for Remarks

Percentage	Interpretation
Above80%	Very high prevalence
70%-80%	High prevalence
60%-70%	Moderate Prevalence
50%- 60%	Low prevalence

Ho3 : Cyberbullying has no significant impact on mental and emotional wellbeing of youth.

TABLE 4: IMPACT OF CYBERBULLING ON MENTAL AND EMOTIONAL WELLBEING IN NORTH 24 PARGANAS DISTRICT.

Sl. No.	Impact Area	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Remarks
1	Anxiety	3.57	1.09	Moderate Impact, Moderate variation
2	Sadness/Depression	3.68	1.05	Moderate –high impact, moderate variation
3	Self esteem	3.78	1.08	High impact, moderate variation.
4	Social Isolation	3.55	1.10	Moderate Impact Moderate ,Variation.
5	Academic /daily life impact	3.68	1.13	Moderate – High Impact, Moderate variation.
6	Stressed	3.86	0.91	High impact, Low Variation
7	Fear/ Insecurity	3.61	1.02	Moderate - High impact , Moderate variation.

Table 4 shows the impact of cyberbullying on mental and emotional wellbeing of youth in North 24 Parganas District. The result show that cyberbullying has a moderate to high impact on mental and emotional wellbeing. The highest impact is seen in stress (Mean=3.86) and self –esteem (Mean=3.78) which means many students feel stressed and their confidence is affected due to cyberbullying. Sadness/ depression (mean=3.68), academic and daily life impact (Mean=3.68) also show a moderate to high impact, it means cyberbullying affects both emotional and daily life activities. Fear /insecurity (Mean=3.61) and anxiety (Mean=3.55) show moderate impact and social isolation (Mean= 3.55) indicates that some students feel isolated.

The standard deviation values are around 1 which indicates that the responses are moderately consistence. While stress (S.D = 0.91) shows low variation.

Overall, the findings indicates that cyberbullying has a significant negative impact on mental and emotional wellbeing among youth.

Ho4 : There is no significant difference in cyberbullying experience between male and female students.

TABLE 5: CYBERBULLYING EXPERIENCE BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE

Cyberbullying Experience	N	S.D	MEAN	MEAN DIFFERENCE	T.VALUE	CRITICAL T	P.VALUE	REMARKS
Male	100	2.82	26.17	0.87	2.11	1.65	0.03	Significant
Female	100	3	25.3					

An independent samples t-test was conducted to determine a statistically significant difference in cyberbullying experience between Male and Female respondents. The results showed that Male (M = 23.17, SD = 2.82) and Females (M = 25.3, SD = 3) had similar mean scores, with a mean difference of only 0.87.

The calculated t-value of 2.11 is greater than the critical t-value (2.009 for a two-tailed test), and the p-value of 0.03 is less than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Hence, the null hypothesis (Ho4) is rejected, indicating that there is statistically significant difference in cyberbullying experience between genders.

The result indicates that there is a difference between male and female students in cyberbullying experience in North 24 Parganas district. Male students have a slightly higher mean score than female, it means they experience more than female.

Conclusion:

The present study executed in North 24 Parganas District demonstrates that cyberbullying is highly prevalent among youth and it occurs in various forms and platform. Mainly it occurs through social media and messaging platforms. The findings of this study indicates that cyberbullying has a moderate to high negative impact on mental and emotional wellbeing of youth. The study also reveals that there is significant difference between male and female youth in North 24 parganas district. Based on this result it is suggested that school should create awareness programme, counselling support, and strict rules against cyberbullying. Parents and teachers are also playing a major role to reduce cyberbullying among youth. They also guide students to use digital platform safely. To reduce cyberbullying organise some preventive measure and proper steps to ensure safer online environment for youth.

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